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Research Article

**DIAGNOSTIC ACCURACY OF ULTRASONOGRAPHY IN
ACUTE APPENDICITIS TAKING LAPAROTOMY FINDINGS
AS A GOLD STANDARD**¹Dr. Reema Abdul, ²Waseem Iqbal, ³Dr. Neelam Raza¹Medical officer, Civil hospital singal ghizer.²THQ Hospital Murree³House officer, DHQ Hospital Rawalpindi**Article Received:** May 2020**Accepted:** June 2020**Published:** July 2020**Abstract:**

Acute appendicitis is a medical emergency and causes abdominal pain which results in surgery. The diagnosis of the appendicitis is clinical, based upon the sign and symptoms present in the patients. For diagnostic purpose ultrasound is considered one of the available options. Ultrasound is widely used because of many reasons like accuracy, availability, cost effective and minimal time-consuming procedure helps to minimize the complications of the surgeries and also help to avoid negative laparotomies. With the advancement in the ultrasound technology the results have become sensitive and specific in diagnosing the acute appendicitis in patients. The cross-sectional study was conducted in the Lahore General Hospital Radiology Department from the period of January 2019 to July 2019 involving 125 patients. Laparotomy results were set as a gold standard after the diagnosis of the acute appendicitis both clinical and radiological using USG. The positive predictive value was 98 % and negative predictive value of the study was 80 %. The sensitivity of the USG was 95 % and the specificity of USG was 91 % and the overall accuracy of the ultrasonography in detecting the acute appendicitis was 95%.

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INTRODUCTION:

Acute appendicitis is a medical emergency resulting in abdominal surgery. It is the inflammation of the inner lining of appendix. The inflammation becomes the cause of lower abdomen pain. The pain is directly linked with inflammation, when the inflammation enhances pain become severe. (2) It can happen to anyone but it is common from 10 to 30 years of age and the gold standard of treatment is the laparotomy of the abdomen. The assessment of appendicitis is clinical, based upon the following sign and symptoms

- Pain observed in the lower right side of the abdomen
- Pain starts from navel and moves around in right abdomen
- Pain increases due to movement and cough
- Nausea, lack of appetite and vomiting is observed
- Fever presence and increases with the severity of condition
- Bloating of abdomen

Early diagnosis of the acute appendicitis based upon the clinical presentations helps in the avoidance of the morbidity and the mortality among the patients. Perforation of appendicitis is considered high risk for the patient's life. In addition to the clinical examination's ultrasonography helps to avoid the laparotomy of the normal appendices even with the presence of the symptoms. In past 20 to 30 percent of the laparotomies were performed upon patients who have normal appendix based on clinical presentations. (3) The clinical diagnosis error usually observed in the women of reproductive age and in the older age group. The negative laparotomies have declined due to the accuracy of USG and CT scans for the acute appendicitis diagnosis. The late diagnosis or delayed surgeries due to many personal reasons can cause perforation of appendices which is life threatening. (4)

For the diagnosis of the acute appendicitis in addition to laboratory test the Computed tomography and ultrasounds are used. CT scans are expensive and needs the intravenous and oral contrast agents. It is also not widely available

although the sensitivity and specificity is high. While the USG is considered widely available cost-effective option for timely diagnosis of acute appendicitis and other causes of lower abdominal pain. The results of ultrasound in diagnostic accuracy are highly sensitive and specific.

At present the high frequency transducers have made the diagnosis accurate and negative laparotomies have reduced considerably. The benefits of ultrasounds are noninvasive, safe; discomfort to patient is minimum, widely available and is easily repeatable without any harm. It has helped in avoidance of laparotomies in children and in women of fertile age. The purpose of the study is to analyze the accuracy of the ultrasound setting laparotomy as a gold standard.

METHODOLOGY:

The study was conducted in Radiology Department of Lahore General Hospital. Total of 125 patients were included in the study from January 2019 to July 2019 who came after the clinical examination and having the symptoms of lower abdomen pain, tenderness, vomiting, fever and increased leucocytes count. The ultrasound of the patients were performed peri appendiceal abscess was identified and inflammation was observed. Linear array transducer having multiple frequencies from 7.5MHz-10.0MHz was used for the patient's partially or fully filled bladder. Graded compression techniques were applied in both longitudinal and transverse plane. The inflamed and enlarged diameter in case of appendicitis was measured greater than 6mm and the thickness of cecal wall was 5 mm or above. Patients who have negative USG results were not referred for the surgeries. Only patients with appendicitis identification from USG were referred for laparotomies which were set as a gold standard for the study.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

Total of 125 patients participated in the study having clinical symptoms of acute appendicitis. 100 patients who were positive in ultrasound scans were referred for surgeries as shown in the table below.

Table 1 USG results

Sample size	Positive Laparotomy	True Positive	False Positive	True Negative	False Negative
125	105	98	2	20	5

From the above table 1 it is clear that out of 125 patients' 100 patients shown positive result in ultrasound about the presence of the acute appendicitis. The results of laparotomy showed that 2 out of 100 patients were false positive. It means identified positive on USG and were negative in laparotomy. The patients who were not referred for surgeries when opted for surgery due to persistent pain and the results for five were acute appendicitis positive after laparotomy. It means 5 patients were false negative and the true negative patients were 20 having abdominal pain due to other reasons and also negative on USG report. Following table 2 is about the ultrasound results found in patients.

Table 2

Ultrasound Results	Cases#	Percentage
Appendix presence	100	95%
Probe tenderness	105	100%
Diameter	100	95%
Fluid presence	70	66.7%
Appendicolith	8	7.7%
Sub mucosal integrity loss	30	28.6%
Appendicular mass	35	33.3%
Caecal thickening	70	66.7%

The purpose of the study was to check the accuracy of the USG in identification of acute appendicitis in patients'. The specificity and the sensitivity was calculated about USG results which show that sensitivity and specificity both are high. Therefore, USG is highly recommendable and reliable. The diagnostic accuracy is also high in addition to the positive predictive value and negative predictive value as is shown in table 3

Table 3

Ultrasound Evaluation	Results
Sensitivity	95%
Specificity	91%
Diagnostic Accuracy	95%
Negative Predictive Value	80%
Positive Predictive value	98%

The sample size age group was wide from minor to older people. The minor age group was from 1 to 10 years total 4.8% of the patients were from this group and 11% were from 50 plus years of age. The majority was in their teens. Male patients were higher in ratio as compared to female patients. The ratio was 60 to 40. The high frequency probe was used for identification of acute appendicitis.

The studies conducted by Lewis et al (9) and Addis et al (2) showed that teen age is at high risk of getting acute appendicitis and is more common in male as compared to female. Abdomen pain was observed in 99% of the patients, tenderness was observed in 93% of the patients and the pain points identified by the patients help to detect the appendicitis during USG.

Puylaert was the one who introduced graded compression technique in the acute appendicitis diagnosis which helps to identify the inflammation and peri appendicel abcess. The normal appendix is easily compressible and diameter is less than 6 mm. The diameter of acute appendicitis is higher than 6 mm.

The present study results were comparable regarding specificity and sensitivity of USG results with the studies conducted by Tarzan Z et al, Skanne et al, Hahn et al and Pulaert et al. Their specificity values ranged from 90 to 100 % and sensitivity value range were from 80 to 95%. The study results showed that 98 patients were true positive after the surgery and 2 cases were false positive after the

surgery which was positive in USG reports. 15 cases were negative on the USG reports but when laparotomy was done due to the persistent abdomen pain. Five were positive in acute appendicitis after laparotomy. These cases were considered false negative. 20 cases were true negative for acute appendicitis.

CONCLUSION:

Acute Appendicitis is surgical emergency. When the patients after clinical examination and positive sign and symptoms of acute appendicitis were referred for ultrasound. The laparotomy results showed that accuracy of diagnosis was significantly high. The laparotomy was taken as a gold standard for measuring the accuracy of the USG diagnosis. USG helps to avoid the negative laparotomies based upon only the clinical symptoms.

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